

ISic0477

Epitaph for Placida

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Castronuovo di Sicilia

Provenance

Known since the 17th century; previously in the church of S. Maria dell'Udienza on Colle S. Vitale, subsequently transferred to the Chiesa Madre of the Holy Trinity in Castronovo, where it is built into the wall

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Castronuovo di Sicilia

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 45 cm

Width 50 cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line

1
: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to

2
: mm

Text

1. Hic requiesci
2. t in pace Placi
3. dia univera univiria
4. qu(a)e vix(it) ann(os) pl(us) m(inus)
5. XXXV p(ost) c(onsulatum) Basili v(iri) c(larissimi)
6. per indi(c)tione(m)
7. quarta(m) ann
8. o XXVIII

Apparatus

Text of CIL 10.7196

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491702

EDCS 21900537

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7196 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

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Giustolisi, V. 1999. Petra: atlante delle antiche strutture rupestri dell'alta valle del Platani (Castronovo). Palermo. At 16 figs.1-2

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